

PV panels tilt angle assessement under restricted area conditions and resilience in a Romanian case

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Abstract— This paper performs an assessment of PV panels solutions under restricted area conditions, by considering tilt various angles and partial shading avoidance, also with focus on high self-production and increased resilience of the prosumer or of the energy community. It is proposed an algorithm using average price of energy used by building owner based on a mix between price obtained from PV panels and energy market price. Breakeven return of invest are highlighted, having PV panels technology price, energy market price and tilt angle variations as main parameters of the analysis. The analysis is made for locational conditions specific for Bucharest - Romania, while the results can be extrapolated also for regions with similar geographical situations.

Keywords—PV panels, tilt angle, restricted area, partial shading, self-consumption, resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of photovoltaic (PV) production is a promising technology which may cover in the future more than 50% of a country energy need. Even if there are concerns on the higher than acceptable area for such high deployment of PV plants, there are many studies which show that in fact only a small part of a country area (usually less than 2%, even down to 1%) is necessary to produce entire energy of specific countries [1]. However, the deployment of a large amount of PV panels may be not possible in populated places, especially for prosumers and energy communities, where for reasons of resilience and self-sufficiency it is useful to use an existing but limited area to get as much as possible energy from it.

It is the intention of this paper to analyze solutions which allow increased local production in limited area production, by also considering economic model.

In this respect, for the same area one can have a higher or a lower density of PV panels, by changing the distance between rows of panels based on the tilt angle and the condition to have no shading during the worst situations, to accept a certain shading in short time of the day during the winter period.

The problem has been developed in previous studies [2][3][4]. Moreover, analysis having installation guidelines can be found as reference, e.g. [5], while partial shading is also assessed in several studies, such as [6][7][8]. Analysis of tilt angle has been widely studied in various works, such as

[8][9][10][11]. However, coupling PV panels arrangement with limited area conditions has been less treated in previous works.

The paper is coupling the PV arrangement with yearly production and shading avoidance or reduced partial shading situations over the year, by calculating return of investment (ROI) by coupling with grid-supplied energy versus local energy production and with resilience.

II. PV PANELS SLOPE VERSUS AREA USE

Figure 1 shows the monthly PV production in Bucharest (exact location the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest main location), at the optimum year-long fixed angle of 34 degrees, based on calculations made with the calculation tool from [12].

Fig. 1. Monthly energy output from a 34° fix-angle 1 kWp PV in Bucharest

The calculation of the total width of a row of panels and is based on the parameters shown in Figure 2

Fig. 2. Geometry for rows of PV panels

In this Figure the inputs are:

- α , as being the minimum angle of the sun, which is exceeded during the winter period between representative hours of the day.

β , the tilt angle of the PV panel

d , the PV dimension on short side

P , the pathway between two PV rows

L_1 , the total length of a PV row, which includes PV panel (segment A_1C) and pathway P (segment CA_2)

By having as inputs d and α , L_1 and P can be calculated based on relations (1) to (3)

$$A_1C = d * \cos(\beta) \quad B_1C = d * \sin(\beta) \quad (1)$$

$$L_1 = A_1C + A_2C = A_1C + B_1C / \tan(\alpha) = d * \cos(\beta) + d * \sin(\beta) / \tan(\alpha)$$

$$L_1 = d[\cos(\beta) + \sin(\beta) / \tan(\alpha)] \quad (2)$$

$$P = A_2C = d * \sin(\beta) / \tan(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

Calculation on real PV production as per Figure below shows that during a typical day in December we have 92.3% of energy during 6 hours centred to mid-day, 96.2% during 6.5 hours and during 7 hours it is produced 98% of the total daily energy. This suggests that the shadow may be accepted in limited situations outside mid-day centred 6 to 7 hours during December.

Fig. 3. PV production in a December sunny day

It can be seen that a number of 6 to 7 hours without shading during winter time is harnessing the most of the possible energy.

III. CASE STUDY

A number of tilt angles of the PV panels have been chosen, respectively 10, 15, 20, 25 and 35 degrees, and based on above relations the geometry of each design has been calculated. Moreover, based on yearly energy obtained from [12] considering each of the chosen tilt angle, the total energy on an area of 200 m² has been calculated, starting from a real case study which needed to be assessed.

With the interactive tool from [13], the minimum angle of the sun is obtained on 21st of December, with 22.17° at noon (hour 12:13) while shadow appears in the second part of the day at 13.39 with $\alpha=19.4^\circ$. One month earlier (21st of November) $\alpha=21.96^\circ$ and at noon $\alpha=25.71^\circ$. In order to consider as much as possible, the wintertime, it has been considered a minimum angle of 20°, corresponding to building shading moment around the most unfavourable day of the year, with the lowest sun position at middle of the day.

The maximum installed power is obtained for a tilt of 10 degrees. For comparison, for each other situation it has been calculated a difference of energy which need to be purchased from the grid. A number of 20 years has been considered for the Return of Investment (ROI), for a long-term strategic thinking.

The used area for the case study is presented in Figures 4 and Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Case study PV area at University Politehnica of Bucharest using the interactive tool [13]

Figure 5 gives a 3D view of the same area.

Fig. 5. Case study PV area as a 3D view using [14]

Two Scenarios have been considered in two context situations:

- Scenario 1 considers today end-user usual price at low voltage, if energy is purchased from the grid, which is currently around 12 cents/kWh.

- Scenario 2 considers either future higher price of energy purchased from the low voltage grid, or even today higher prices in Western countries, which could be considered to be 20 cents/kWh or more (20 cents has been chosen as an average future price over Europe, after price equalisation within large European markets).

Each of these scenarios have been also enriched with two price levels for the PV investments, a sub-variant 1 for today PV prices and a subvariant 2 for tomorrow better prices due to new technologies such as perovskite or hybrid solutions, which may consider a reduction factor for the PV prices $K2=0.8$, which may be reachable e.g. in the next 3 years.

Table below gives figures related to Scenario 1.1, with a ROI of 20 years.

TABLE I. CALCULATIONS IN SCENARIO 1.1 FOR ROI=20 YEARS

	Significance	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5
1	α (min Sun angle)	20	20	20	20	20
2	β (Tilt angle of PV panels)	10	15	20	25	35
3	P (pathway between rows)	0.48	0.71	0.94	1.16	1.58
4	L1 (total width of a PV row)	1.46	1.68	1.88	2.07	2.40
5	P_{tot} =PV power on the area (kW/200m ²)	23.1	20.1	17.9	16.3	14.1
6	C_{ROI} =ROI period total cost [k€/lifetime]	40.5	36.3	33.1	30.7	27.3
7	E_{ROI} = PV production on ROI period [MWh]	483	460	433	401	355
8	E_{Gr} =Energy needed to be purchased from grid	0.0	22.8	50.4	82.1	127.9
9	C_{gr_1kWh} = spec.cost of grid energy [€/kWh]	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
10	Total cost of energy from grid [€]	0	2,734	6,049	9,849	15345
11	C_{TROI} =Total cost of energy over ROI period (PV prod +grid)	40,533	39,009	39,166	40,546	42,623
12	C_{1kWh} =user spec.energy cost over ROI period [€/kWh]	0.084	0.081	0.081	0.084	0.088

The following formulas apply for Table 1: L1 has been calculated with formula (2), while pathway P is calculated with (3); the PV power on the chosen area of 200 m² is given by the formula:

$$P_{tot} = A / (Width_{PV_panel} * L1 / P_{PV_panel}) \quad (4)$$

where $Width_{PV_panel}$ is the horizontal width of the panel (selected as being 1.64 m), L1 is calculated before, A is the total area selected to be 200 m² and P_{PV_panel} is the nominal power of the PV panel at 1000 W/m². C_{ROI} , as ROI period total cost considers specific price of 1 kW of mounted panels over the ROI period C_{ROI_1kW} , which include price of mounting accessories, montage work and maintenance cost, $C_{ROI_1kW} = 1750$ Euro/m² for the entire lifetime, with a ROI period ROI = 25 years:

$$C_{ROI} = C_{ROI_1kW} * ROI \quad (5)$$

E_{ROI} , as being the PV production on ROI period, is calculated with the formula:

$$E_{ROI} = E_{PV_1kW_1year} * P_{tot} * ROI \quad (6)$$

where $E_{PV_1kW_1year}$ depends on the tilt angle and is based on information from [12].

E_{Gr} is the energy needed to be purchased from grid, to cover for the versions V2-V5 the difference from energy obtained at highest density (V1, tilt of 10 degrees, $P_{tot}=23.1$ kW) and the other versions when for the same area A it is obtained a lower energy per lifetime):

$$E_{Gr}(Vx) = E_{LT}(Vx) - E_{LT}(V1) \quad (7)$$

where x =2, 3, 4, 5 and corresponds to V2-V5. To be noted that $E_{Gr}(V1)$ is zero, as it is the base case.

The table considers the specific cost of grid energy as being $C_{gr_1kWh} = 0.12$ Euro, which corresponds to an average final price for residentials in Romania, labelled also as Scenario 1. Higher prices will be considered in Scenario 2.

C_{TROI} , which is the total cost of energy over lifetime (PV system costs + costs of energy taken from the grid), is based on

$$C_{TROI} = C_{ROI} + E_{Gr} * C_{gr_1kWh} \quad (8)$$

C_{1kWh} , as user specific energy cost over lifetime [€/kWh] is the final result for the whole calculation, giving the equivalent price of kWh by considering all factors.

Figure 6 gives a graphical view of the algorithm of calculating the user specific energy.

Fig. 6. Algorithm for calculation of the user specific energy price

One can see that on the left side is the reference case with highest PV panels density, which correspond to the lowest considered tilt angle $\beta=10^\circ$ and that for this situation the whole energy is harvested from the PVs. This reference case corresponds to the highest use of the given S area (100 m² in the study). From the left to the right the tilt angle is increased up to the angle which gives the highest energy/kWp over the year, however in order to avoid PV inter-shading, the density decreases and the total energy harvested from PVs on the same area is also decreased, while the difference is obtained from the energy market (line 10 from the Table 1), bringing a mix of

energies which defines the user specific energy cost over ROI period (line 12 from the Table 1).

As an assessment on the table results, it can be seen that the best user energy price is obtained for tilt angles between 15 and 20 degrees. However, the 15 degrees solution has also around 6% more power and yearly energy. Choosing one of these solutions may have also to do with resilience needs, if the user cannot find additional areas for covering the total energy.

By considering ROI with the values 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 20 and 25 years, the superposed graphs for Scenario 1.1 by using the above β values can be seen in Figure 7.

An important information relies in the fact that there is a breakeven regarding the average price of mixed energy (PV based on investment and purchased from grid, at market price) at a ROI around 16 years.

Fig. 7. Average energy price for different PV panels tilt angles and payback time for Scenario 1.1 (today energy price from the grid, today PV price: $K=1$)

Figure 8 is pointing the Scenario 1.2, when evolving technology is reducing the PV production price with 20% (a factor $K=0.8$), which is a realistic assumption for 3 to 5 years from now.

Fig. 8. Average energy price for different PV panels tilt angles and payback time for Scenario 1.2 (today energy price from the grid, $K=0.8$)

One can see that for lower cost of PV investment ($K=0.8=80\%$), the breakeven ROI is slightly smaller, around 14 years, which suggest that the policy for making investments is more important than the grid price evolution.

Figure 9 shows similar evolution for energy price for a future higher price from grid level, due e.g. to market equalisation between east and west European countries and eventually to higher costs for the process of full decarbonisation. Breakeven ROI is at around 8 years

Fig. 9. Average user energy price for different tilt angles and payback time for Scenario 2.1 (higher energy price from the grid, today PV price: $K=1$)

Figure 10 shows the Scenario 2.2, where there is in the future the same higher price from grid level as per Scenario 2.1, while there is also a reduction of PV price. Breakeven ROI is also at around 8 years. By comparing Scenarios 2.1 and 2.2, it can be seen that technology price is not anymore as important as it is the energy market price.

Fig. 10. Average user energy price for different tilt angles and payback time for Scenario 2.2 (higher price from the grid, $K=0.8$)

For all Scenarios, it can be seen that grid energy price is the main factor for the PVs, and that the higher it is the grid price, the lower is the ROI for a local PV investment.

The assessment shows that in all situations it is better to have higher PV panels density when approaching longer ROI policies, while future reduction of PV technology may keep valid the same type of results.

To be noted that even the tilt angle of 10 degrees looks as the most attractive, the panels maintenance of such design would be extremely difficult, as the pathway P between rows of PV panels is too small (0.33m in table 1), while the angle of 15 degrees (or nearby values) show in the study to be a balanced solution, with an acceptable width $P=0.71$ m and PV power for the 200 m² of 20.1 kW.

Figure 11 makes a synthetises of the results presented above, by showing the breakeven for lower energy price (12c/kWh) and for higher energy price (20c/kWh) for the same PV panels cost.

Fig. 11. Scenarios 1.1 and 2.1 breakeven comparison for today PV technology

It can be seen that higher market price is beneficial for reduction of ROI and increases the attractiveness for local production. This situation suggest that future increase in energy market price can accelerate complete payback of today investments at current energy prices.

Figure 12 gives a final overview of the influence of the two factors: market energy price and PV panels price, at their studied limits: low market energy price and today capital costs - CAPEX (scenario 1.1) and higher market energy price and future (lower) CAPEX (scenario 2.2).

Combined with previous figures, it can be deduced that the most important factor is the energy market price, while PV panels price reduction plays also some role. Moreover, future scenarios in an uncertain environment (with possible higher prices of energy, also to sustain greener energy production over the entire year) are making more attractive local production facilities and high density of PV panels on available roofs.

Fig. 12. Overview of the influence of the studied factors: market energy price and PV panels price

It can be seen also that in all the scenarios and sub-scenarios, for any ROI higher than the breakeven value, the average energy price for the local entity is lower if the PV density is higher, meaning with lower tilt angle. This observation suggests that the best situation will be with the lowest β angle (in this study considered as being 10 degrees, which is a usual lowest angle for PV installations), however higher β angles such as 15 or 20 degrees may have also better characteristics in terms of dust self-cleaning during rains [15] and easier cleaning of snow in hard winters.

IV. ASPECTS OF LOCAL RESILIENCE

Energy resilience is a factor with a raising importance, which start to have official support in the smart cities and smart communities' paradigm.

Even if the above calculations do not address benefits from resilience, a simple way to be considered can be to increase the costs of non-delivered energy from main grid, as a mitigation during this temporary shortage need e.g. local energy production with much higher costs (classic generation sets using for shorter time gas as fuel for missing energy is usually associated with much higher costs of energy, e.g. 40c/kWh).

In this view, a higher resilience can be simulated by a higher cost of energy price from the market, which brings the subject in the framework of already made calculations. It means that the need for higher resilience has similar effects with higher energy price, thus this can also reduce the ROI of the local investment.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper performs an assessment of PV panels solutions under restricted area conditions, by considering tilt various angles and partial shading avoidance, also with focus on high self-production and increased resilience. The assessment is valid for the limited place for PV panels, which is a usual situation in urban places. While in the situation without any space limitations the best situation is for optimal tilt angle β around 35 degrees, while the highest power for the selected area is obtained by a tilt angle zero, the average price of energy

obtained by PV production combined with support energy purchased from the market has an evolution which depends mainly on market energy price and PV capital costs (CAPEX). In all situations, for higher ROI than the breakeven the average energy price for the local entity is lower if the PV density is higher - thus with lower tilt angle. This observation suggests also that investment in local energy production, such as energy produced from local PV panels, should be seen as a strategic investment which is expected to be recovered in a period between 8 and 16 years.

Moreover, if local resilience is also considered, a component of the ROI reduction can be associated to the resilience as well, making even more attractive the investment in local energy production. It means that strategic driven investment complemented by local resilience requests high PV density, thus lower tilt angles, while limitations are still given by other factors, such as dust self-clearing, which is reducing operational costs.

The analysis is made for locational conditions specific for Bucharest - Romania, however the results can be extrapolated also for regions with similar geographical situations.

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